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United States Senate

COMMITTEE ON
HOMELAND SECURITY AND GOVERNMENTAL AFFAIRS
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July 10, 2024

Via Email (Steven@DrQuay.com)

Steven C. Quay, M.D., Ph.D.
Former Faculty
Stanford University School of Medicine
Redacted address

Dear Dr. Quay:

Enclosed are post-hearing questions that have been directed to you and submitted for the official record from the hearing that was held on June 18, 2024, titled "Origins of COVID-19: An Examination of Available Evidence."

In order to ensure a complete hearing record, please include each question in full before each response and return your written response on or before August 9, 2024, via email to the committee's chief clerk, Laura Kilbride, at laura_kilbride@hsgac.senate.gov.

If you have any questions, please contact Laura Kilbride, Chief Clerk, at 202-224-9586. Thank you for your prompt attention to this request.

Sincerely,

Gary C. Peters
Chairman

GCP:lwk

Enclosure

Post-Hearing Questions for the Record

Submitted to Dr. Steven Quay, MD, PhD from Senator Roger Marshall

Origins of COVID-19: An Examination of Available Evidence: June 18, 2024 Hearing

1. In 2002 in Guangdong province, China, SARS illnesses emerged as multiple genetic lineages of a coronavirus, in different cities, at different times over several months. Correct?

- a. Yes. The following chart shows the seven locations of separate outbreaks and the timing of these events. The chart begins in November 2001 and ends in April 2003:

Source: Xu RH, He JF, Evans MR, Peng GW, Field HE, Yu DW, Lee CK, Luo HM, Lin WS, Lin P, Li LH, Liang WJ, Lin JY, Schnur A. Epidemiologic clues to SARS origin in China. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2004 Jun;10(6):1030-7. doi: 10.3201/eid1006.030852. PMID: 15207054; PMCID: PMC3323155.

With SARS1, you can see a slow, evolutionary process of the virus starting in civets and raccoon dogs, acquiring a few mutations in the Spike Protein that allow low pathogenicity infection of civets, then high pathogenicity in civets but still low pathogenicity in humans, and finally the epidemic virus in humans. From the first case in bats, it took 7 mutations to first infect humans and 27 mutations to become epidemic in humans. That is, when it first infected humans it has only 26% of the mutations it needed to be an epidemic strain. Here is a chart of that progression:

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Source: Kan BWang MJing HXu HJiang X, Yan MLiang WZheng HWan KLi Q, Cui B, Xu YZhang EWang HYe JLi G, Li M, Cui ZQi XChen KDu L, Gao K, Zhao Y, Zou X, Feng Y, Gao Y, Hai RYu DGuan Y, Xu J2005. Molecular Evolution Analysis and Geographic Investigation of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus-Like Virus in Palm Civets at an Animal Market and on Farms. *J Virol*79: <https://doi.org/10.1128/jvi.79.18.11892-11900.2005>

2. **Epidemiological data showed that many infections were linked to contact with infected animals at restaurants and markets where the case clusters originated. Am I correct?**

Yes. The following table shows the occupation of the index cases from the Xu et al. paper cited above:

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Table 6

Case series of index cases by municipality in SARS epidemic, Guangdong, China, November 2002–April 2003^a

Case no.	City	Sex	Age	Occupation	Date of onset	Animal contact	Secondary transmission
Case 1	Foshan	M	45	Administrator and village leader	Nov 16, 2002	Yes	Yes
Case 2	Heyuan	M	34	Restaurant chef	Dec 10, 2002	Unknown	Yes
Case 3	Jiangmen	M	26	Factory worker	Dec 21, 2002	No	No
Case 4	Zhongshan	M	30	Restaurant chef	Dec 26, 2002	Yes	Yes
Case 5	Guangzhou	M	49	Office worker	Jan 2, 2003	No	Yes
Case 6	Shenzhen	M	46	Office worker	Jan 15, 2003	No	Yes
Case 7	Zhaoqing	F	39	Market vendor	Jan 17, 2003	Probably	Yes

Here 3 of 7 index cases are work in either the market or in restaurants.

- 3. Following the zoonotic transfers to humans early in the Guangdong epidemic, more than 50% of the communicable Human to Human infections were in Health Care workers and family members providing intimate care to the SARS patients, allowing for adaptation to humans over many months until it left China by travel. Isn't this the accepted theory of the SARS pandemic of 2002-2004?**

The combined incidence in Health Care workers and family members was highest at 50% in January 2003, early in the epidemic, and then declined over the next months to 27%.¹

- 4. The 2002 SARS epidemic was quelled by 2004 using public health measures of isolation and quarantine, but a few new zoonotic transfer cases emerged in 2004 and occupational infections were also documented. Similarly, Human MERS CoV infections were epidemiologically associated with infected Camels, and despite some international travel related clusters, such as what occurred**

¹ Xu et al. Ibid.

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in Korea, the MERS virus has been slow to adapt to become more communicable. Am I correct in these descriptions?

Yes, with clarification. In addition to isolation and quarantine, for the SARS epidemic, the sale of civet cats was banned, and the Chinese government culled thousands of civet cats in Southern China in 2004.² MERS has never had an R_0 that is greater than 1.0, meaning it has never achieved epidemic potential.

5. In the 4 years since the emergence of COVID19, is there any epidemiological data documenting human COVID19 cases with exposure to SARS-CoV-2 infected animals?

No, for the simple reason that the predicate requirement for this question, a SARS-CoV-2 infected animal, has never been found that could not be traced to a **human-to-animal** infection. No animal has ever been infected de novo with SARS-CoV-2.

6. SARS-CoV-2 emerged in the city of Wuhan as a unique genotype already well adapted and highly communicable in humans. Is this consistent with the emergence of SARS and MERS? Are humans generally susceptible to other animal coronaviruses?

As previously stated, SARS1 had only 26% of the amino acids in the Spike Protein that were found in the strain that became epidemic. MERS has never become able to sustain human-to-human transmission. On the other hand, a detailed study of the 200 amino acids in the receptor binding domain of SARS-CoV-2 showed that the amino acids were highly optimized for binding to human ACE2, the receptor for SARS-CoV-2. Specifically, in a study that tested all possible different amino acids at each position in the 200 amino acids, only 0.5% of amino acid changes improved ACE2 binding. The remaining 99.5% amino acids changes either did not improve ACE2 binding or made it worse.³ This could only have happened with a long period of infection of cells with the human ACE2 and then selection for the best adapted viruses.

² <https://www.reuters.com/article/economy/china-in-civet-cat-crackdown-to-prevent-sars-idUSPEK105396/>

³ Starr TN, Greaney AJ, Hilton SK, Ellis D, Crawford KHD, Dingens AS, Navarro MJ, Bowen JE, Tortorici MA, Walls AC, King NP, Veester D, Bloom JD. Deep Mutational Scanning of SARS-CoV-2 Receptor Binding Domain Reveals Constraints on Folding and ACE2 Binding. Cell. 2020 Sep 3;182(5):1295-1310.e20. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2020.08.012. Epub 2020 Aug 11. PMID: 32841599; PMCID: PMC7418704.

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- 7. Recent peer reviewed research, and a 2017 graduate thesis by a Wuhan Institute student shows that the genetic family in which SARS-CoV-2 lies, comes from Yunnan Province in SW China, over 1000 miles from Yunnan, and further West into SE Asia, correct?**

Yes, with clarification.

It is universally accepted that the bat viruses that are closest to SARS-CoV-2 either come from Yunnan Province or from even further away from Wuhan, in northern Laos, about 1400 miles from Wuhan. It is also established that the Wuhan Institute of Virology had collected bat fecal samples from both locations from 2013 to at least 2017.

In the WHO report⁴, Dr. Shi of the WIV reported:

“The team has collaborated internationally since 2004. About 19,000 samples had been collected, coronaviruses were detected in about 13% (2481 positive for CoV) of the tested samples by RdRp sequencing and triaged according to phylogeny. Clade 4 SARSr-CoVs only found in Yunnan.” Note: SARS-CoV-2 comes from Clade 4.

- 8. The 2017 thesis by the WIV student showed that this family of viruses was not found in 20 other regions of China, most specifically not in Wuhan, Hubei Province. So is it reasonable to hypothesize that animals infected with SARS-CoV-2 were transported 1000 miles to Wuhan, where it emerged in the unusual way it did, without causing infections in the intervening provinces of SW China?**

Yes. Let’s look first at the Huanan Seafood Market in Wuhan. Only one vendor in that market had any animals from Yunnan Province and those animals were bamboo rats. Neither this vendor nor any bamboo rats were infected with SARS-CoV-2.

⁴ Page 130. WHO-convened Global Study of Origins of SARS-CoV-2: China Part. Joint WHO-China Study 14 January-10 February 2021. Joint Report - ANNEXES

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Wild animals from Yunnan Province were tested for SARS-CoV-2 genetic sequences. A total of 1287 samples from 27 different species were all negative for SARS-CoV-2.⁵

Farmed animals from Yunnan Province were tested for SARS-CoV-2 infection, looking for antibodies. 379 samples were negative for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies.⁶

Yunnan livestock and poultry samples were also tested and were negative.⁷

529 pig and poultry samples from Yunnan were tested for SARS-CoV-2 genetic material and were negative.⁸

In conclusion, no animals from Yunnan Province have ever been found to have been infected by SARS-CoV-2, whether measuring genetic material or testing for antibodies as evidence of a previous infection.

- 9. The intervening provinces between Yunnan and Wuhan in SW China have a population of over 300 Million people who are served by thousands of markets, many of which contain live animal stalls, yet there were no cases of SARS illnesses reported in the years and months prior to the 2019 Wuhan outbreak. Doesn't this argue against Dr. Garry's Pathway #2?**

Yes it does. And the pattern of spread of SARS-CoV-2 outward in time and space in China is inconsistent with even a single animal to human infection in any province other than Wuhan. See the time-dependent pattern in this graph, showing a spread from Wuhan Province and not Yunnan Province, as would be predicted by Dr. Garry's Pathway #2:

⁵ WHO-convened Global Study of Origins of SARS-CoV-2: China Part. Joint WHO-China Study. 14 January-10 February 2021. Joint Report

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Ibid.

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Source: <https://weekly.chinacdc.cn/article/id/e53946e2-c6c4-41e9-9a9b-fea8db1a8f51>

10. Following the 2002 SARS Pandemic, China formed a sentinel network of hospitals and labs in Southern China to monitor for unusual respiratory diseases. They have reported cases of bird flu, travel acquired MERS, and other respiratory diseases, including the 2012 cases of SARS in 6 Miners in Mojiang county, Yunnan, and 4 tourists presenting with SARS following visits to the karst caves in Yunnan, a popular tourist destination. China contributes this data to the WHO Disease Outbreak Notifications (DON reports). Other than these 10 cases of SARS like illnesses, no other cases of SARS were reported between 2012 and 2019. Again, doesn't this support that Dr. Garry's pathway #2 is also highly unlikely?

The premise of this question is incorrect.

From 2005 to 2018 China did not report a single SARS-related human infection to the WHO or, in fact, in any publications. This is made more remarkable by the very fact that we now know that the miners in Mojiang were determined to be infected with a SARS-related virus, transmitted from bats. This is the first ever known human SARS infection directly from a bat and yet the Chinese did NOT report this to the world.

The secret research by the WIV into these mines for virus sampling and the work on RaTG13 before 2020 that was never disclosed provide important evidence that favors a laboratory origin for SARS-CoV-2.

11. Serology studies were conducted by the WIV and EHA to assess exposure to SARS like coronaviruses in high risk populations in SW China (ref. [Serological Evidence of Bat SARS-Related Coronavirus Infection in Humans, China | Virologica Sinica \(springer.com\)](#)). Only 2.8% of the people surveyed had a

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statistically relevant serological reactivity to SARS related viruses. Sera from patients confirmed as having SARS infections during the 2002 outbreak were used to establish the positive control range. The WIV researchers used over 200 serum samples from residents of Wuhan to establish the negative serology baseline. The WIV/EHA authors stated “As a control, we also collected 240 serum samples from random blood donors in 2015 in Wuhan, Hubei Province more than 1000 km away from Jinning (Fig. 1A) and where inhabitants have a much lower likelihood of contact with bats due to its urban setting. None of the donors had knowledge of prior SARS infection or known contact with SARS patients.” Would you all agree that this argues against the plausibility of Dr. Garry’s pathway #1 occurring in Wuhan?

Yes it does.

A study⁹ of retained blood samples in Wuhan blood banks reported on the incidence of SARS-CoV-2 antibodies prior to January 2020. A total of 88,517 samples from all 76,844 blood donors who gave blood from September 1, 2019, to December 31, 2019 were tested for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. The conclusion of the report is: “Our findings showed no SARS-CoV-2-specific antibodies existing among blood donors in Wuhan, China before 2020, indicating no evidence of transmission of COVID-19 before December 2019 in Wuhan, China.”

A statistical analysis of this data, using the calculated incidence in Wuhan based on finding no infected patients, was performed. The 95% Confidence Interval for the number of cases in Wuhan with these data is between zero and 429 infected people from September 1, 2019, to December 31, 2019. Other methods of estimating the number of infected people in Wuhan in the fall of 2019 arrive at very similar numbers.

**I certify that these answers are true and correct, to the best of my knowledge.
Signed,**

⁹ hang, Lei Zhao, Yan Xiao, Tingting Xu, Lan Chen, Yan Cai, Xiaojing Dong, Conghui Wang, Xia Xiao, Lili Ren, Lunan Wang, Serosurvey for SARS-CoV-2 among blood donors in Wuhan, China from September to December 2019, Protein & Cell, Volume 14, Issue 1, January 2023, Pages 28–36, <https://doi.org/10.1093/procel/pwac013>